

NUMERICAL STUDY OF CONVECTIVE MHD FLOW OF A TERNARY NANOFLUID OVER A STRETCHING SHEET WITH VISCOUS AND JOULE HEATING EFFECTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the steady, two-dimensional convective magneto hydrodynamic (MHD) boundary layer flow of a ternary ($\text{Cu} - \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 - \text{SiO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and hybrid nanofluids ($\text{Cu} - \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$) over a convectively heated elastic sheet. The governing equations with convective boundary conditions are solved numerically using a mathematical software tool, employing the RKF-45 method along with the shooting technique. The plots of velocity and temperature profiles for both $\text{Cu} - \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 - \text{SiO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu} - \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for various parameters are captured. The Grashof number (G) enhances velocity and depreciates temperature in both nanofluids. It is noticed that higher

dissipative energy (E_c) larger the velocity and temperature in the entire flow region. Skin friction (τ) increases and Nusselt number (Nu) decreases at the stretching sheet in both ternary as well as hybrid nanofluid with the increasing values of $\Phi/R_d/E_c/Q_s$. This paper endorses that ternary nanofluid has an excellent thermal accomplishment over the hybrid nanofluid.

KEYWORDS: Ternary nanofluid, hybrid nanofluid, convective boundary conditions, skin friction, Nusselt number.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticle research has gained considerable attention due to its potential applications in fields such as medicine, optics, and electronics. The study of squeezing flow between parallel boundaries has intrigued many researchers and engineers because of its relevance to various engineering processes, metal fluid purification, and industries like food and chemicals. This phenomenon also finds applications in shaping and squeezing operations. Nanofluids, which consist of solid particles ranging from 1 to 100 nanometers dispersed in base fluids, have shown promise in enhancing the thermal conductivity and heat transfer properties of the base fluids (as noted by Choi and Eastman^[1] and Buongiorno.^[2]) Further research by Eastman et al.^[3] demonstrated the measurement of thermal conductivity in Cu/C₂H₆O₂ nanofluids. Sheikholeslami and Ganji^[4] explored the impact of particle shape on forced convective flow of nanofluids in the presence of Lorentz forces. Additionally, several studies have investigated the behaviour of nanofluids under varying conditions, as discussed in references such as Yin et al.^[5] and Zhang et al.^[6]

A few years later, researchers identified that combining multiple nanosized particles in a clear base fluid enhances its thermal properties, leading to the development of what are now called "hybrid nanofluids." These fluids are particularly effective in cooling high-temperature thermal systems and are widely used in applications such as solar energy systems, heat exchangers, generator cooling, transformers, heat pipes, and nuclear technology. Experimental studies by Jana et al.^[7] brought further insights into hybrid nanofluids. It was observed that the heat conduction efficiency of these fluids improves significantly with an increased volume fraction of nanoparticles, a phenomenon earlier reported by Suresh et al.^[8] Other researchers have also explored the potential of hybrid nanofluids, as noted in studies.^[9–17] For instance, Satya Narayana et al.^[18] investigated the flow of Cu-Al₂O₃/H₂O hybrid nanofluids over a porous, stretching sheet under the influence of temperature-dependent viscosity and viscous dissipation. Their findings showed that the velocity profile of hybrid nanofluids improves with a higher convection parameter. Furthermore, due to variable viscosity, hybrid nanofluids achieve faster boundary convergence compared to Al₂O₃/H₂O nanofluids. Extensive research on hybrid nanoparticle mixtures, their applications, and developments can be found in references.^[19–20]

In recent years, researchers have combined three distinct types of nanoparticles within a base fluid to create a new class of nanofluids known as "ternary hybrid nanofluids." This

innovative development emerged due to the growing industrial demand for advanced cooling solutions with superior thermal properties. To address these requirements, a trihybrid nanofluid was introduced, offering enhanced thermal characteristics. Mousavi et al.^[21] explored the behaviour of a trihybrid nanofluid composed of TiO_2 , CuO , and MgO suspended in water. Sahoo et al.^[22] proposed a novel correlation aimed at improving the viscosity of such fluids. Further interest in ternary hybrid nanofluids has been spurred by recent investigations.^[23–27] Jafar Hasnain et al.^[28] examined the thermal behaviour of water- and engine oil-based ternary nanofluids containing nanoparticles of various shapes over both linear and nonlinear stretching sheets. Their findings indicated that increasing the nanoparticle volume fraction led to higher temperatures in ternary nanofluids compared to hybrid nanofluids, for both linear and nonlinear stretching scenarios. Adnan and Ashraf^[29] investigated the influence of a magnetic field on trihybrid nanofluid flow under convective heating conditions, comparing the results with hybrid nanofluid flow. The advancements in trihybrid nanofluid research have drawn significant attention and continue to encourage further studies.^[30–32]

Aly and Pop^[33] analysed stagnation point flow and heat transfer characteristics of hybrid nanofluids, factoring in slip conditions and the effects of viscous dissipation. Their study included a stability analysis near the endpoint within a regime exhibiting dual solutions. Lund et al.^[34] focused on the stability of copper-alumina/water hybrid nanofluids over a stretching or shrinking surface, also considering viscous dissipation. Using the three-stage Lobatto IIIa method, they identified two solutions, determining that the first is stable while the second lacks stability. Afridi et al.^[35] explored thermal behaviour in the boundary layer flows described by Blasius and Sakiadis for hybrid nanofluids. Their work included the study of two hybrid nanofluid types— $\text{Cu-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{water}$ and $\text{Cu-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{kerosene oil}$ —and reported that temperature rises in both systems.

The present study focuses on the analysis of convective MHD flow of ternary nanofluid ($\text{Cu} - \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 - \text{SiO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$) over a stretching sheet accounting for viscous and joule heating dissipations. Here partial differential equations are solved numerically by employing RKF method with shooting scheme. Results so arrived are strongly cope up with the existing results. This paper also compares the effects of different parameters on ternary ($\text{Cu} - \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 - \text{SiO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and hybrid ($\text{Cu} - \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$) nanofluids.

2. Formulation of the problem

In this paper the steady, two-dimensional convective magneto hydrodynamic (MHD) boundary layer flow of a ternary nanofluid over a convectively heated elastic sheet is examined. The ternary nanofluid comprises copper (Cu) nanoparticles, iron oxide (Fe_3O_4), and silicon dioxide (SiO_2) dispersed in water as the base fluid. The schematic representation of the flow configuration is provided in Fig. (1). The X-axis is aligned with the flow direction, while the Y-axis is perpendicular to it. The velocity along the surface is defined as $U_w(x) = ax$, where a is a constant with dimensions of inverse time (t^{-1}). The surface temperature is T_w , and the ambient temperature is T_∞ . A uniform transverse magnetic field of strength B_0 is applied perpendicular to the X-axis. Incorporating viscous and Joule heating effects and conventional boundary conditions, the governing equations for the ternary nanofluid flow are derived as follows.

Fig. 1: Geometry of the flow configuration.

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{\rho_{thnf}} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\rho_{thnf}} B_0^2 u + \frac{(\rho\beta)_{thnf}}{\rho_{thnf}} g(T - T_\infty) \quad (2)$$

$$(\rho c_p)_{thnf} v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = k_{thnf} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + Q(T - T_\infty) - \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} + 2\mu_{thnf} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 + (\sigma_{thnf} \mu_e^2 H_0^2) u^2 \quad (3)$$

The appropriate boundary conditions are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u = ax, v = 0, -k_{hnf} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = h_f (T_w - T) \text{ at } y = 0 \\ u \rightarrow 0, T \rightarrow T_\infty \text{ as } y \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

The radiative heat term q_r , based on the Roseland approximation, is expressed as follows

$$q_r = -\frac{4\sigma^*}{3k^*} \frac{\partial T^4}{\partial y} \quad (5)$$

The representation of T^4 around T_∞ using Taylor's series is expressed as

$$T^4 = 4T_\infty^3 T - 3T_\infty^4 \quad (6)$$

Then we have

$$\frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} = \frac{-16\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{3k^*} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \quad (7)$$

Table 1: Values of nanoparticles.

Nanofluid particles				Base fluid
Thermal & physical properties	Cu	Fe ₃ O ₄	SiO ₂	Water
C _p (j/kg K)	385	670	765	4179
ρ (kg m ³)	8933	5180	2270	997.1
k (W/m K)	400	9.7	1.4013	0.6071
βx10 ⁻⁵ (1/k)	1.67	0.5	0.056	21.0
σ(s/m)	5.96×10 ⁷	2.5×10 ⁻⁴	3.5×10 ⁶	5.5×10 ⁻⁶

Table 2: Properties of nanoparticles.

Thermal & physical properties	Ternary, Hybrid & Mono nanofluids
Viscosity (μ) N.s / m ²	$\mu_{hnf} = \frac{1}{\mu_f^{-1}(1-(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3))^{2.5}}, \mu_{hnf} = \frac{1}{\mu_f^{-1}(1-(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2))^{2.5}}, \mu_{nf} = \frac{1}{\mu_f^{-1}(1-\Phi_1)^{2.5}}$
Density(ρ) Kg / m ³	$\rho_{hnf} = (1-(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3))\rho_f + \Phi_1\rho_{s1} + \Phi_2\rho_{s2} + \Phi_3\rho_{s3},$ $\rho_{hnf} = (1-(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2))\rho_f + \Phi_1\rho_{s1} + \Phi_2\rho_{s2}, \rho_{nf} = (1-\Phi_1)\rho_f + \Phi_1\rho_{s1}$
Specific heat (C _p), J / k	$(\rho C_p)_{hnf} = (1-(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3))(\rho C_p)_f + \Phi_1(\rho C_p)_{s1} + \Phi_2(\rho C_p)_{s2} + \Phi_3(\rho C_p)_{s3}$ $(\rho C_p)_{hnf} = (1-(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2))(\rho C_p)_f + \Phi_1(\rho C_p)_{s1} + \Phi_2(\rho C_p)_{s2}$

	$(\rho Cp)_{nf} = (1 - \Phi_1)(\rho Cp)_f + \phi_1(\rho Cp)_{s1}$
Thermal expansion $(\rho\beta)$	$(\rho\beta)_{thnf} = (1 - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3))(\rho\beta)_f + \Phi_1(\rho\beta)_{s1} + \Phi_2(\rho\beta)_{s2} + \Phi_3(\rho\beta)_{s3}$ $(\rho\beta)_{hnf} = (1 - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2))(\rho\beta)_f + \Phi_1(\rho\beta)_{s1} + \Phi_2(\rho\beta)_{s2}$ $(\rho\beta)_{nf} = (1 - \Phi_1)(\rho\beta)_f + \Phi_1(\rho\beta)_{s1}$,
Thermal conductivity y (k) W / m.k	$\frac{k_{thnf}}{k_{mf}} = \frac{\Phi_1 k_{s1} + \Phi_2 k_{s2} + \Phi_3 k_{s3} + 2(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)k_f + 2(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)(\Phi_1 k_{s1} + \Phi_2 k_{s2} + \Phi_3 k_{s3}) - 2(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)^2 k_f}{\Phi_1 k_{s1} + \Phi_2 k_{s2} + \Phi_3 k_{s3} + 2(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)k_f - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)(\Phi_1 k_{s1} + \Phi_2 k_{s2} + \Phi_3 k_{s3}) + (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)^2 k_f}$ $\frac{k_{hnf}}{k_{nf}} = \frac{\Phi_1 k_{s1} + \Phi_2 k_{s2} + 2(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2)k_f + 2(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2)(\Phi_1 k_{s1} + \Phi_2 k_{s2}) - 2(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2)^2 k_f}{\Phi_1 k_{s1} + \Phi_2 k_{s2} + 2(\Phi_1 + \Phi_2)k_f - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2)(\Phi_1 k_{s1} + \Phi_2 k_{s2}) + (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2)^2 k_f}$ $\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} = \frac{\Phi_1 k_{s1} + 2(\Phi_1)k_f + 2(\Phi_1)(\Phi_1 k_{s1}) - 2(\Phi_1)^2 k_f}{\Phi_1 k_{s1} + 2(\Phi_1)k_f - (\Phi_1)(\Phi_1 k_{s1}) + (\Phi_1)^2 k_f}$
Electrical conductivity y (σ)	$\frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\sigma_{hnf}} = \frac{\sigma_{s1}(1 + 2\Phi_1) + \sigma_{hnf}(1 - 2\Phi_1)}{\sigma_{s1}(1 - \Phi_1) + \sigma_{hnf}(1 + \Phi_1)}$, $\frac{\sigma_{hnf}}{\sigma_{nf}} = \frac{\sigma_{s2}(1 + 2\Phi_2) + \sigma_{nf}(1 - 2\Phi_2)}{\sigma_{s2}(1 - \Phi_2) + \sigma_{nf}(1 + \Phi_2)}$ $\frac{\sigma_{nf}}{\sigma_f} = \frac{\sigma_{s3}(1 + 2\Phi_3) + \sigma_f(1 - 2\Phi_3)}{\sigma_{s3}(1 - \Phi_3) + \sigma_f(1 + \Phi_3)}$

In the expressions provided Φ_1, Φ_2 and Φ_3 are solid volume fractions of **Cu, Fe₃O₄** and **SiO₂** respectively. The velocity and temperature profiles are obtained using the similarity transformations outlined below.

$$u = axf'(\Omega), v = -\sqrt{av_f} f(\Omega), \Omega = \sqrt{\frac{a}{\nu_f}} y, \theta(\Omega) = (T - T_\infty)(T_w - T_0)^{-1} \tag{8}$$

The similarity variables defined in equation (8) fulfil the conditions of equation (1), ensuring they accurately describe the fluid flow. By substituting the similarity variables from equation (8) into equations (1) through (4) and utilizing the relationship in equation (7), the following system of equations is derived:

$$f_{\Omega\Omega\Omega} - (A_1 A_2)[(f_\Omega)^2 - ff_{\Omega\Omega}] - A_1 A_6 M^2 f_\Omega + (A_1 A_3 G)\theta = 0 \tag{9}$$

$$A_1[A_5 + \frac{4}{3}R_d]\theta_{\Omega\Omega} + A_1 A_4 P_r f \theta_\Omega + A_1 P_r Q_s \theta + E_c P_r (f_{\Omega\Omega})^2 + A_1 A_6 P_r M^2 E_c (f_\Omega)^2 = 0 \tag{10}$$

Where $G = \frac{\beta_f g(T_w - T_o)}{a^2 x}$ is the Grashof number, $M^2 = \frac{\sigma_f B_o^2}{\rho_f a}$ is the magnetic field parameter,

$R_d = \frac{4\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{k^* k_f}$ is the Radiation parameter, $Pr = \frac{\mu_f (C_p)_f}{k_f}$ is the Prandtl number,

$Q_s = \frac{Q}{(\rho C_p)_f a}$ is the heat source parameter, Here $f_\Omega = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \Omega}, \theta_\Omega = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \Omega}$ and so

on. $A_3 = (1 - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)) + \Phi_1 \frac{(\rho\beta)_{s1}}{(\rho\beta)_f} + \Phi_2 \frac{(\rho\beta)_{s2}}{(\rho\beta)_f} + \Phi_3 \frac{(\rho\beta)_{s3}}{(\rho\beta)_f}$ is the Eckert number.

Dimensionless boundary conditions

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f_{\Omega}(0) = 1, f(0) = 0 \quad \theta_{\Omega}(0) = -\frac{B_i}{A_5} (1 - \theta(0)) \\ (11) \quad f_{\Omega}(\infty) = 0, \theta(\infty) = 0 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

where

$$B_i = \frac{h_f}{k_f} \left(\frac{V_f}{a} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ is the Biot number.}$$

The terms are derived from the above equations as follows:

$$A_1 = (1 - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3))^{2.5}$$

$$A_2 = (1 - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)) + \Phi_1 \frac{\rho_{s1}}{\rho_f} + \Phi_2 \frac{\rho_{s2}}{\rho_f} + \Phi_3 \frac{\rho_{s3}}{\rho_f}$$

$$A_3 = (1 - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)) + \Phi_1 \frac{(\rho\beta)_{s1}}{(\rho\beta)_f} + \Phi_2 \frac{(\rho\beta)_{s2}}{(\rho\beta)_f} + \Phi_3 \frac{(\rho\beta)_{s3}}{(\rho\beta)_f}$$

$$A_4 = (1 - (\Phi_1 + \Phi_2 + \Phi_3)) + \Phi_1 \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s1}}{(\rho C_p)_f} + \Phi_2 \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s2}}{(\rho C_p)_f} + \Phi_3 \frac{(\rho C_p)_{s3}}{(\rho C_p)_f}$$

$$A_5 = \frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f}, A_6 = \frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\sigma_f}$$

The two most important quantities of practical importance in the current inquiry are skin friction and Nusselt number which are given by

$$\text{Skin friction } (\tau) = \frac{\text{Re}^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{A_1} f_{\Omega\Omega}(\Omega)$$

$$\text{Nusselt number (Nu)} = -A_5 \text{Re}^{\frac{1}{2}} \theta_{\Omega}(\Omega)$$

$$\text{Where } \text{Re} = \frac{a^2 x}{V_f} \text{ is the Reynolds number.}$$

Numerical procedure

The velocity equation,^[9] temperature equation,^[10] and the associated boundary conditions^[11] are solved numerically using a mathematical software tool, employing the RKF-45 method along with the shooting technique. These equations, being higher-order with two-point

boundary conditions, are converted into a system of first-order initial value problems to facilitate the solution process.

We consider

$$\frac{df}{d\Omega} = f_1, \frac{d^2f}{d\Omega^2} = \frac{df_1}{d\Omega} = f_2, \frac{d^3f}{d\Omega^3} = \frac{df_2}{d\Omega} = f_3$$

$$\frac{d\theta}{d\Omega} = g_1, \frac{d^2\theta}{d\Omega^2} = \frac{dg_1}{d\Omega} = g_2$$

$$f_3 - (A_1A_2)[f_1^2 - ff_2] - A_1A_6M^2f_1 + (A_1A_3)G\theta = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$A_1[A_5 + \frac{4}{3}R_d]g_2 + A_1A_4P_rfg_1 + A_1P_rQ_s\theta + E_cP_r(f_2)^2 + A_1A_6P_rM^2E_c f_1^2 = 0 \quad (13)$$

With

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f_1 = 0, f = 0, g_1 = -\frac{B_i}{A_5}(1-\theta) \text{ at } \Omega = 0 \\ f_1 \rightarrow 0, \theta \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \Omega \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14)$$

The transformed initial value problem is solved by estimating the missing values using the shooting method after selecting the appropriate parameters. A step size of 0.1 is used for the calculations, with an error tolerance of approximately 10^{-6} .

Comparison

Table 3: A comparison of the current findings with those of Haritha et al. is made regarding the heat transfer rate for various values of P_r when $R_d = E_c = 0$.

P_r	Manjunatha et al.[36]	Haritha et al.[37]	Present values
2	0.9113	0.9114	0.9112
6.13	1.7596	1.7595	1.7597
20	3.3539	3.3538	3.3534

OUTCOMES & DISCUSSION

The effect of key variables on the velocity and the temperature is illustrated in the figures 2a-2b, 3a-3b, 4a-4b, 5a-5b, 6a-6b, 7a-7b. The parameter values adapted for this investigation include: $\Phi = 0.01, G = 0.2, M = 0.1, R_d = 2.5, Q_s = 0.5, E_c = 0.1, P_r = 6.2, B_i = 0.1$. This work explores how these parameters influence the flow and the temperature profiles inside the ternary nanofluid system under the given conditions.

Fig.(2a) represents the variation of axial velocity (f') with nanoparticle volume fraction Φ . The fluid velocity (f') depreciates when Φ (solid volume fraction) increases in both nanofluids. Enhancement in Φ heightens the fluid boundary layer, lowering the fluid velocity. The magnitude of f' in ternary nanofluid is smaller than that of hybrid nanofluid. Fig.(2b) represents the variation of temperature (θ) with Φ . The fluid temperature upsurges with the higher values of Φ . The thermal conductivity of the nanofluid is a function of the thermal conductivity of both the base fluid and the nanoparticles. Increasing the nanoparticle volume fraction results in the increase in the conductive heat transfer coefficient and consequently the convective heat transfer. Increasing the thermal conductivity leads to the increase in the efficiency of the fluid heat transfer. This agrees with the physical behaviour that, when the volume fraction parameter Φ enhances, the thermal conductivity increases and consequently the thermal boundary layer thickness increases. This may be attributed to the fact that thickness of thermal boundary layer enhances on par with the larger values of Φ . The temperature in ternary nanofluid is greater than that in hybrid nanofluid.

Figs.(3a & 3b) exhibit the impact of G on f' & θ . It is noted that an increment in G leads to the enhancement in the magnitude of f' and depreciation in θ . This can be attributed to the fact that rising G thickens the momentum boundary layer while thermal boundary layer becomes thin in entire flow region.

The impact of magnetic parameter (M) on f' & θ is exhibited in figs. (4a & 4b). It is noted that f' experiences depreciation when M augments. This is due to the fact that the thickness of momentum boundary layer decays when M grows. In case of θ , opposite effect is observed when M increases in both ternary and hybrid nanofluids. This is in accord with the physics of the problem, since the application of transverse magnetic field results in resistive type force (The Lorentz force) similar to the drag force which tends to resist the fluid flow and thus reduces its f' and enhances its θ .

Figs.(5a-5b) exhibit the influence of thermal radiation (R_d) on f' , θ . An increasing in R_d results to augmentation in magnitude of f' and θ in entire flow region. This may be attributed to the fact that increasing in R_d enhances the thickness of momentum and thermal boundary layers in both nanofluids.

The effect of dissipative energy (E_c) has been observed in figs. (6a & 6b). From the graph we notice that higher E_c larger the velocity (fig.(6a)). This may be due to the fact that the thickness of momentum boundary layer experiences grow for larger values of E_c . A higher E_c indicates that more kinetic energy is converted into internal energy through dissipation. This leads to increased heat generation within the flow. Consequently, temperature profile becomes steeper near the solid boundaries where viscous dissipation is significant, causing the temperature of the fluid to rise (fig. (6b)).

It is identified from the graphs that the values of f' & θ in ternary nanofluid are relatively greater than those in hybrid nanofluid.

Skin friction (τ) increases and Nusselt number (Nu) decreases at the stretching sheet in both ternary as well as hybrid nanofluid with the increasing values of $\Phi/R_d/E_c/Q_s$. In case of M/Bi , both τ and Nu are depreciated in both nanofluids at the stretching sheet while G appreciates τ and Nu. (Table. (4)).

It is noted from the graphs that the values of Nu in ternary nanofluid are relatively greater than those in hybrid nanofluid .

Fig. 2: Effect of Φ on (a) Velocity and (b) Temperature.

Fig. 3: Effect of G on (a) velocity and (b) temperature.

Fig. 4: Effect of M on (a) velocity and (b) temperature.

Fig. 5: Effect of R_d on (a) velocity and (b) temperature.

Fig. 6: Effect of E_c on (a) velocity and (b) temperature.

Table 4: Effects of different parameters on Skin friction (τ) and Nusselt number(Nu) for ternary and hybrid nanofluids at $\Omega = 0$

Parameter	Ternary Nanofluid		Hybrid Nanofluid	
	$\tau(0)$	Nu(0)	$\tau(0)$	Nu(0)
Φ	-0.86882	-0.09757	-0.87987	-0.08979
	-0.85768	-0.10567	-0.87921	-0.10213
	-0.84646	-0.11414	-0.87818	-0.11473
G	-0.82517	-0.09217	-0.83567	-0.08482
	-0.79961	-0.04214	-0.80963	-0.03706
	-0.77624	-0.01627	-0.78585	-0.01232
M	-0.82517	-0.09217	-0.83567	-0.08482
	-0.8537	-0.16771	-0.86632	-0.16102
	-0.92523	-0.41401	-0.94255	-0.41021
Rd	-0.82517	-0.09217	-0.83567	-0.08482
	-0.77146	-0.11868	-0.78116	-0.11109
	-0.74315	-0.12844	-0.75223	-0.12100
Qs	-0.82517	-0.09217	-0.83567	-0.08482
	-0.58882	-0.29700	-0.60158	-0.28141
	-0.28018	-0.59333	-0.29524	-0.56645
Pr	-0.82517	-0.09217	-0.83567	-0.08482
	-0.86222	-0.07094	-0.87283	-0.06409
	-0.89633	-0.04986	-0.90689	-0.04363
Ec	-0.82517	-0.09217	-0.83567	-0.08482
	-0.80446	-0.11011	-0.81467	-0.10247
	-0.78566	-0.12650	-0.79562	-0.11859
Bi	-0.82517	-0.09217	-0.83567	-0.08482
	-0.84734	-0.14127	-0.85653	-0.13029
	-0.86184	-0.17037	-0.87018	-0.15744

CONCLUSION

From this study we conclude that

- f' decays while θ upsurges for higher values of Φ in both ternary and hybrid nanofluids.
- Magnetic parameter (M) decays f' and enhances θ in ternary as well as hybrid nanofluid. Reverse effect is observed in case of G .
- E_c and R_d enhance both velocity and temperature in the entire flow region.
- M / Bi decays rate of heat transfer in ternary and hybrid nanofluids at the stretching sheet G enhances it.

Nomenclature

u, v velocity components in x, y directions

B_o induced magnetic field

τ skin friction

q_r radiative heat flux

Q_s heat source parameter

Nu Nusselt number

Pr Prandtl number

C_p specific heat at constant pressure

M Magnetic field parameter

T temperature of the fluid

T_w temperature of the wall

T_∞ ambient temperature

σ^* Stefan-Boltzmann constant

σ electrical conductivity of the fluid

ρ density of the fluid

Φ_1 solid volume fraction of copper particles

Φ_2 solid volume fraction of iron oxide particles

Φ_3 solid volume fraction of silicon dioxide particles

f fluid

nf nanofluid

hnf hybrid nanofluid

$thnf$ ternary hybrid nanofluid

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